

1 **IGFN1 functions in melanoma resistance.**

2
3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730
7

8 Citations

- 9 1. Li, X., Baker, J., Cracknell, T., Haynes, A.R. and Blanco, G., 2017. IGFN1_v1 is required for
10 myoblast fusion and differentiation. PLoS One, 12(6), p.e0180217.
11 2. Baker, J., Riley, G., Romero, M.R., Haynes, A.R., Hilton, H., Simon, M., Hancock, J., Tateossian,
12 H., Ripoll, V.M. and Blanco, G., 2010. Identification of a Z-band associated protein complex involving KY,
13 FLNC and IGFN1. Experimental cell research, 316(11), pp.1856-1870.
14 3. Cracknell, T., Mannsverk, S., Nichols, A., Dowle, A. and Blanco, G., 2020. Proteomic resolution of
15 IGFN1 complexes reveals a functional interaction with the actin nucleating protein COBL. Experimental
16 cell research, 395(2), p.112179.
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28